

COMPARISON OF THE SUCCESS OF B LYNCH SUTURE VERSUS
INTRAUTERINE BALLOON TAMPONADE IN POSTPARTUM
HAEMORRHAGE DUE TO UTERINE ATONY

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Abstract

Introduction: Among the appropriate treatments for PPH include tranexamic acid, uterotonics, and uterine massage. The high rates of morbidity and mortality associated with PPH are further compounded by the limited access to these essential medicines in low-resource settings. Uterine compression sutures (B Lynch sutures) and intrauterine balloon tamponade are two alternative methods that are increasingly being used to avoid hysterectomy and its after effects.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of intrauterine balloon tamponade with B Lynch suture in treating postpartum hemorrhage.

Materials and Procedures: One hundred individuals between the ages of 18 and 40 who experienced postpartum hemorrhage following vaginal delivery were included. Patients with placental abruption, perineal injuries, retained products of conception, genital tract rips, and heparin/warfarin medication were not included. B Lynch suture was used on group 1 patients. Foleys catheters of No. 24 Fr size, were inserted via the cervix into the uterine cavity to provide intrauterine balloon tamponade to group 2 patients. The researcher herself monitored each patient, noting whether they were successful or not.

Results: The average age in groups B Lynch suture group and intrauterine balloon tamponade group was 29.06 ± 4.37 and 28.94 ± 4.47 years, respectively. The majority of the 59 patients, or 59.0%, were in the 18–30 age range. Efficacy (in terms of not having a hysterectomy) was observed in 44 (88.0%) patients in B Lynch suture group and 35 (70.0%) patients in intrauterine balloon tamponade group.

Conclusion: In comparison to intrauterine balloon tamponade, our study found that B Lynch suture is more effective at managing postpartum hemorrhage.

INTRODUCTION

Bleeding more than 500 milliliters after vaginal delivery or more than 1000 milliliters after cesarean delivery is known as postpartum hemorrhage. One to five percent of all deliveries

are affected by this severe, potentially fatal disease. Poorer nations have a higher incidence.¹ Given that the mortality rate for postpartum patients ranges from 0.3% to 15%, postpartum

hemorrhage is one of the main causes of death for women.² In order to minimize maternal death, PPH is an obstetric emergency that needs to be diagnosed quickly and treated well. The phrase "golden hour" has recently been used to describe the treatment of primary PPH. To provide the best chance of survival, resuscitation must be started during the "golden hour." If the patient is not successfully revived within the first hour, the chances of survival drastically drop.^{3,4}

Uterine atony is the most common cause of postpartum hemorrhage, accounting for 80% of cases, while there are other potential causes as well.⁵ Risk factors for PPH include infection, subinvolution of the placental location, retained products of conception, hematocrit < 30%, and inherited coagulation problems.⁶ Uterine balloon tamponade (UBT), uterine arterial embolization, oxytocins, prostaglandins, uterine massage, uterotonics, tranexamic acid, and other surgical procedures have all been used to treat refractory bleeding.⁷ Among the appropriate treatments for PPH include tranexamic acid, uterotonics, and uterine massage.⁸ The high rates of morbidity and mortality associated with PPH are further compounded by the often limited access to these essential medicines in low-resource settings. B Lynch sutures and balloon tamponade are two alternative methods that are increasingly being used to avoid hysterectomy and its aftereffects.⁸

Uterine balloon tamponade has been included as a second-line treatment for PPH in recent years. To provide a tamponade effect, a balloon is inserted into the uterus and inflated during the UBT process.⁹ Numerous balloon catheter types, such as the Sengstaken-Blakemore tube, the Bakri balloon, the Roush balloon, and the Foleys catheters modified for intrauterine tamponade, have been documented in the literature. By collecting blood outflow into a collection bag, balloon tamponade avoids blood storage inside the uterus, which could cause uterine atony, and also gives a precise estimate of bleeding. IUBT is a straightforward technique that clinicians with little experience can easily do and can help decrease continuous uterine blood loss.^{9,10}

There were previously very few randomized controlled trials comparing intrauterine balloon tamponade and B Lynch in PPH. Many patients in Pakistan's rural areas present with postpartum hemorrhage as a result of multiparity and unattended home births. We are unable to perform a hysterectomy in any of them following the failure of standard medical care. This study compares the outcomes of B Lynch suture and intrauterine balloon tamponade for postpartum hemorrhage due to uterine atony in the local population because there isn't any local literature that contrasts the two methods at the moment. Then, based on the study's findings, these specific patients could be given a method that has a higher success rate to lower maternal morbidity and mortality. Additionally, some useful suggestions could be included in our standard practice guidelines for treating these patients in a way that preserves fertility and prevents hysterectomy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

100 multiparous patients (50 in each group) between the ages of 18 and 40 who had postpartum hemorrhage (defined as blood loss after caesarean section > 1000 ml) after caesarean delivery participated in this randomized controlled trial from June 1, 2024, to November 30, 2024, with approval from the ethical review committee. Using the WHO calculator for two proportions, the sample size was determined to be 100, or 50 cases in each group, with a 5% level of significance, 80% research power. Patients who had ruptured uterus, were on heparin or warfarin medication, had a coagulation condition (INR>1.3), retained products of conception, or placenta previa (measured on USG) were not included.

Each woman gave her informed permission. She was assigned to the appropriate group after each chosen case was divided into two groups by using random number tables. Patients in group 1 received B Lynch suture. Initially, bimanual compression was used, and concurrently, an aide swabbed the vagina to ensure proper bleeding control. In order to reduce trauma and achieve or facilitate compression, the two suture lengths were drawn taut with the help of bi-manual compression. About 4 cm from the

cornua, the suture was about vertical. Four Foleys catheters of No. 24 Fr size, with an average balloon capacity of 80–100 ml, were inserted into the uterine cavity to provide intrauterine balloon tamponade to patients in group 2. A total amount of 320–400 milliliters of fluid was created by injecting warm saline into the balloons. The researcher herself monitored each patient, noting efficacy (if bleeding ceased within 30 minutes and no hysterectomy was necessary). A specially created proforma, which is attached at the end, contained all of this data. All of the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. The mean and standard deviation of age and gestational age were calculated. Frequency and percentage were calculated for efficacy (yes/no). The effectiveness of the two groups was compared using chi square, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS:

The study's participants ranged in age from 18 to 40, with a mean age of 28.64 ± 4.26 years. The average age of the women in groups 1 and 2 was 29.06 ± 4.37 and 28.94 ± 4.47 years, respectively. According to Table I, the majority of the patients (59.0%) were between the ages of 18 and 30. According to Table II, the average gestational age was 39.01 ± 1.46 weeks.

According to Table III, efficacy (in terms of avoiding a hysterectomy) was observed in 44 (88.0%) patients in Group 1 (B Lynch suture) and 35 (70.0%) patients in Group 2 (intrauterine balloon tamponade), with a p-value of 0.027 that is statistically significant.

Table-I: Distribution of patients according to age (n=100).

Age (yrs)	Group 1 (n=50)		Group 2 (n=50)		Total (n=100)	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
18-30	29	58.0	30	60.0	59	59.0
31-40	21	42.0	20	40.0	41	41.0
Mean \pm SD	29.06 ± 4.37		28.94 ± 4.47		28.64 ± 4.26	

Table-II: Distribution of patients according to gestational age (n=100).

GA (weeks)	Group 1 (n=50)		Group 2 (n=50)		Total (n=100)	
	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
37-39	31	62.0	31	62.0	62	62.0
40-42	19	38.0	19	38.0	38	38.0
Mean \pm SD	39.04 ± 1.47		39.06 ± 1.45		39.01 ± 1.46	

Table III: Comparison of efficacy between both Groups (n=100).

		Group 1 (n=50)		Group 2 (n=50)	
		Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
EFFICACY	Yes	44	88.0	35	70.0
	No	06	12.0	15	30.0

➤ P value is 0.027 which is statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

There was a dearth of information in the literature comparing these two methods, particularly when placenta previa was included. Therefore, in the current investigation, the efficacy of B Lynch suture and balloon tamponade during cesarean birth in patients with postpartum hemorrhage was compared.

In contrast to the mean age of 25 years discovered in the study by Yousaf et al.¹¹ and 26.4±4.2 years found in the study by Soued et al.¹², the mean age of the patients in this study was 28.64 ± 4.26 years. Likewise, Savcı et al.¹³ discovered that the majority of patients were between the ages of 26 and 30, with a mean age of 27.

The bulk of the 62 patients (62.0%) in this study were between 37 and 39 weeks of gestation, with the mean gestational age being 39.01 ± 1.46 weeks. This indicates that individuals with shorter gestational ages are more likely to experience postpartum hemorrhage. These findings also aligned with those of Tirumuru et al.¹⁴ and Savcı et al.¹³ Our study's mean gestational age mirrored the results of Soued et al.¹², who showed that the average length of pregnancy was 37.81±1.67 weeks, and Kadioglu et al.,¹⁵ who discovered that the average duration of pregnancy was 37.9±3 weeks.

In our study, 44 (88.0%) patients in Group 1 (B Lynch suture) and 35 (70.0%) patients in Group 2 (intrauterine balloon tamponade) experienced efficacy (in terms of averting a hysterectomy), with a statistically significant p-value of 0.027. The results contradicted those of a 2013 study by Kavak et al., which revealed that the balloon tamponade group was more effective than the suture group.¹⁶ Prior research has demonstrated that balloon tamponade and B Lynch suture are more effective individually at preventing postpartum hemorrhage during cesarean sections. When compared to the control group, the proactive use of Bakri balloons during caesarean sections resulted in fewer medical and surgical interventions in a randomized controlled research with 52 patients.¹⁷

In another trial, just two individuals required packing after the researchers used vertical

compression suture on 15 patients.¹⁸ In one study, 95 patients in the experimental group received parallel vertical compression sutures, while 100 patients in the control group received the same procedure. The results showed that compression sutures were a successful surgical technique for securing hemostasis and preserving the uterus.¹⁹

Only three patients suffered postpartum hysterectomy in another trial that included 278 pregnant women; 168 of the 171 women who received vertical compression suture had positive outcomes.²⁰ An investigation by Fatima et al.²¹ in Bahawalpur indicated that B Lynch suture had a higher success than intrauterine balloon tamponade for treating postpartum hemorrhage. According to Kanwal et al.²², the success rate of B Lynch sutures in PPH was 93.7%, which is in line with our findings. Inconsistently, Mohamed et al.²³ found no discernible difference in the success rate between bilateral uterine artery ligation and B Lynch suture in the treatment of PPH. Nonetheless, Shazia et al.²⁴ discovered comparable results about the 83% success rate of B Lynch suture in PPH. According to one study from Pakistan, B Lynch suture had an 83% success rate in managing PPH, while another study found that it had a 91% success rate.^{25,26}

The disparity in success rate could be caused by various factors, including patient selection criteria, technique and time of administration. One benefit of the B Lynch suture is its ease of application and speed. To maximize its effectiveness, it should be tried as soon as feasible, and preventative use should be taken into account in high-risk patients. Because of its greater success rate, B Lynch suture can treat PPH with exceptional results and, when applied promptly, can quickly stop the bleeding.²⁷

A single-center design and a small patient population were two of our study's drawbacks. Even while a variety of data about problems has been gathered, it could not accurately represent the procedure's rate of complications. Therefore, future research should focus on bigger population-based studies with long-term follow-up.

CONCLUSION:

In the treatment of postpartum hemorrhage, this study discovered that B Lynch suture works better than intrauterine balloon tamponade. For these particular individuals, we therefore recommend that the B Lynch suture technique be used as the main strategy in order to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality from postpartum bleeding due to uterine atony.

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